

Analytical Study of Democratic Values in the Constitution of India

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Abstract:

The Research Paper delves into the profound insights and contributions of Dr. Ambedkar regarding democracy, rights, and societal values. It explores the intricate interplay between political, social, and economic dimensions within the constitutional framework. Dr. Ambedkar's emphasis on establishing a robust foundation for democracy, ensuring equality, and fostering a sense of brotherhood in society is meticulously analyzed. The study also delves into the significance of special powers and constitutional provisions for marginalized groups, highlighting the pivotal role of socio-economic rights in shaping a just and equitable democratic system. Through an analytical lens, The Research Paper illuminates Dr. Ambedkar's visionary perspectives on democracy, equality, and the parliamentary system, underscoring the essence of ethical and constitutional principles in shaping a democratic society.

Key words - Liberty, Equality, Social Democracy, Political Democracy, Economic Democracy, Thoughts of Brotherhood.

Introduction:

The architect of the Indian Constitution, presented the constitution to the nation and established a democratic system with it. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar's unique contribution is significant in building modern India. Dr. Ambedkar took great care to deeply analyse and approach the social, political, economic, and cultural disparities in India with a scientific perspective. Dr. Ambedkar took on the significant task of reorganising all these unfair systems. The concept of democracy is not only about material possessions but also about ideology. Dr. Ambedkar had a profound idea when designing a democratic system. Taking into account all the factors of democracy, Dr. Ambedkar has introduced this system to the public via the Constitution. Dr. Ambedkar discusses the advantages and disadvantages of democracy in his writings. Dr. Ambedkar stated that the democratic system outlined in the constitution will not be successful if those in charge of implementing it lack capability. Ambedkar held a firm belief. This research paper endeavours to analyse the study of democratic values in the constitution of India .

Social-Economic Rights-

When considering political democracy, it is important to also consider social and economic democracy. Political freedom loses its significance without economic freedom and opportunities for the less privileged in society. Furthermore, without the elimination of caste discrimination and social injustice, political freedom will hold no value. The French Revolution helped bolster democracy by introducing the ideals of freedom, fairness, and brotherhood. When attempting to discover the timeless aspect of Ambedkar's ideology, one immediately thinks of his dedication to the three values of equality, liberty, and fraternity. The principle of equality is also considered essential.

The resolution of untouchability, the eradication of the caste system, and the dismantling of the religious-cultural values and traditions that supported the caste system all stem from the universal principle of equality. Dr. Ambedkar thought that it was necessary for democracy to empower the untouchables, who lack economic and social opportunities, by offering them a variety of options. If marginalised groups do not have their social and economic rights clearly defined, the dominant class in society will continue to hold power indefinitely. Creating a monopoly within a specific group will unfairly harm those who are less powerful. Dr. Ambedkar firmly believed that by establishing socio-economic justice as the basis of political democracy, democracy has the power to bring about comprehensive change.

Thoughts on Freedom Typically, the idea of 'freedom' is commonly viewed in a negative light. As per Dr. Ambedkar, freedom involves genuine chances, skills, and the capacity for personal and societal growth. Dr. Ambedkar argued that unrestricted negative freedom results in endless personal conflicts, monopolies, and dominance. He thought that favourable social, economic, and physical conditions were necessary in order to enjoy basic rights. To achieve this, the social and economic rights of the existing classes must be restructured. This implies a requirement to redistribute power and wealth. Dr. Ambedkar believes that freedom cannot be fully experienced by just implementing constitutional limitations. There is no guarantee that the ruling class will provide fairness to the oppressed; in fact, they are more likely to further exploit the weaker class. As this class will exploit freedom further, True freedom lies in our state of mind. Having a free mind indicates liveliness. Dr. Ambedkar stated that this freedom should not infringe upon the constitution's

structure. He stated that, in addition to liberty, all individuals are considered equal as per the constitution.

Equality:

Dr. Ambedkar stated that freedom cannot be achieved without equality. Ambedkar thought that the privilege granted to the ruling class by the government was essentially the same as the control of wealthy individuals. The ideas of liberty and fairness go hand in hand, benefiting both individuals and the government, as well as providing chances for societal and economic progress for marginalised groups. Equality is not emphasised in the West, while social, economic, and cultural inequality has become a notable characteristic of India's social framework. Dr. Ambedkar recommended that. There is a greater necessity to ensure equality in India. Equality cannot be achieved unless the roots of socio-economic disparity are dismantled. Dr. Ambedkar had conducted a thorough study of the caste system in India. The aim of Dr. Ambedkar When examining the concept of equality, Dr. Ambedkar endorsed the principles of 'equal suffrage', 'one person, one vote', and 'adult suffrage'. Considering their lack of political rights, marginalised individuals may gain authority, but their ability to impact change once in power is uncertain. Ambedkar had doubts. Equality is about treating everyone the same to ensure that every individual has the same opportunities for personal growth and advancement. Equality involves providing opportunities and establishing suitable circumstances for each individual. When there is a level playing field, the individual or group's intrinsic abilities will be more stimulated and energised, leading society to significantly advance. In a capitalist system, equality is eradicated, while individual freedom is eradicated in a communist system. Dr. Ambedkar was in favour of democratic socialism.

Special powers and constitutional provisions

Dr. Ambedkar believes equality goes beyond just equal opportunities, emphasising the need for special opportunities for marginalised groups. Dr. Ambedkar emphasised the need for a constitutional provision to offer special opportunities, concessions, and protection to socially and economically disadvantaged groups in order to enhance their competitiveness. Dr. Ambedkar incorporated social justice into the Indian Constitution by granting special concessions and protection to the Scheduled Castes and the Educationally Backward Classes, thus enforcing the principle of equality.

Thoughts of brotherhood:

Dr. Ambedkar believes that even though we have established a democratic system founded on freedom and equality, without a sense of brotherhood and social harmony, a genuine human

society cannot be formed. Society functions like a family, and it is essential to foster a feeling of inclusivity and unity among its members. Dr. Ambedkar states that a sense of brotherhood will be fostered in the vulnerable community. All social groups must honour the dignity, equal justice, equal status, and rights of other groups. If a sense of brotherhood is established within society, the ideals of liberty and equality will be safeguarded.

Political Democracy:

Dr. Ambedkar's ideas appear to have been significantly impacted by the French Revolution. The new philosophy of liberty, equality, and fraternity was introduced to the world by the French Revolution. Political democracy took shape as a fresh liberal system was established. By liberating the citizens from the rule of the monarch, power was transferred into the hands of the average person. In the end, the concept of people owning the state system began to gain prominence in the democratic system. The idea of democracy suggests that every member of society has the opportunity to participate in the political system. To elevate the class that has been excluded from political, social, and economic advancements for centuries and to enhance the class as a whole. Ambedkar's aim had turned into, as Dr. stated, that the oppressed group would only be liberated from bondage once they acquired political authority. Ambedkar had a belief. Dr. Ambedkar set up a political party for this purpose. The doctor stated that the establishment of political democracy is necessary to ensure that justice is given to the disadvantaged. Ambedkar's opinion. Dr. Ambedkar believed that in a democratic society, the state should limit its involvement and prioritise safeguarding individual rights as the main objective of governance. A form of political democracy needs to be established where both the majority and minority groups respect and have trust in each other. Dr. Ambedkar suggests that while granting constitutional rights, one must ensure that no injustice is done to any group.

Social Democracy:

Dr. Ambedkar thought that in order for political democracy to thrive, it was essential to establish social democracy. Without altering our traditional social setting, our political rights will hold no significance. Dr. Ambedkar believed that political democracy was partially introduced by the British in India, but they were unsuccessful in creating social democracy. Dr. Ambedkar initiated a social movement for this purpose. The doctor stated that political justice or law will ensure the protection of human rights. Ambedkar did not believe that to be true. Dr. Ambedkar believed that a mutual agreement on human rights in society was crucial for establishing political democracy as the basis for societal harmony.

Economic Democracy:

Just having political democracy in place in the nation won't lead to justice for the citizens or result in genuine democracy. Dr. Ambedkar stated that true justice will be achieved only when social and economic democracy are established. If the person or the group does not have financial power, they will be enslaved indefinitely. Marx's socialist ideology's philosophical basis. Even though Ambedkar did not completely agree, he agreed to the socialist economic program. He thought that parliamentary democracy could bring about state socialism. He believed that democratic socialism was the way to achieve human liberation. In his address to the Constituent Assembly, Dr. Ambedkar pondered the question of how to establish economic democracy. Does this idea have certainty? There is a belief among individuals that there are numerous methods to establish economic democracy. There are individuals who believe in the necessity of a socialist system. This is the most effective method to promote economic democracy. They believe that a socialist government and system are superior. He argues that this arrangement creates economic democracy.

Parliamentary System of Government:

Dr. Ambedkar's political beliefs were influenced by the principles of democracy. Dr. Ambedkar researched the presidential and parliamentary systems of government. In a submission to the Constitutional Committee, he stated his belief that India would not benefit from a parliamentary system but would be better off with a presidential system. However, during the later period, it appears that he supported parliamentary democracy. Dr. Ambedkar believes that using peaceful democratic methods can create economic and social changes in society. Another option for democratic governance besides non-violence is the deliberative process. In a democratic system, choices are determined through talking and deliberating. Decisions are made and implemented by the Executive Board. The parliamentary form of government is the most ideal system for ensuring the welfare of both individuals and society. Dr. Ambedkar stated that the only way for individual life and social change to occur is through the parliamentary system of government. Ambedkar's viewpoint was. The parliamentary system's effectiveness hinges on active citizens, accountable opposition parties, and free, fearless elections. Ambedkar's view was. During the Mahad Satyagraha in 1927, Dr. Ambedkar mentioned the French National Assembly in his speech, suggesting the current assembly should be inspired by it. This assembly must create a similar path for the progress of Hindu society as the one devised by the French for their nation's development and the one embraced by reformed nations.

Conclusion:

Taking the above discussion into account, Dr. Ambedkar believed more in the foundational principles and ideals of parliamentary democracy than its procedural framework. Dr. Ambedkar did not provide the Constitution as a written document but instead focused on establishing a socio-economic foundation for its provisions. He prioritised the political party system, elections, legislature functioning, the government's role in the constitution, as well as societal values like equality, responsible public opinion, constitutional ethics, and social conscience. Ambedkar has emphasised something special.

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